

ENGLISH IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF RUSSIA AND UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: The article examines the processes of the spread of the English language and the formation of the English-speaking environment by the example of the inclusion of foreign language disciplines in the education system of Russia and Uzbekistan. Approaches to teaching foreign languages and language selection in pre-revolutionary Russia, during the Soviet Union and the post-Soviet period are shown. The concepts of introducing English into the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan within the framework of the trilingualism program are presented. New technologies and mass media affect the field of education, and the potential of new technologies is such that they can radically change the practice of teaching foreign languages. It is globalization that retains a significant impact on the study of foreign languages.

Keywords: English, education system, language choice, trilingualism program, foreign language education.

The term "globalization" was first used in 1985, the definition of the term in his works was given by the American sociologist Roland Robertson. According to the scientist, "globalization is a process of increasing influence of various factors of international importance (for example, close economic and political ties, cultural and information exchange) on the social reality in individual countries" [1, 10]. This term can also refer to processes related to the functioning of languages. Linguistic globalization finds its expression, first of all, in the wide spread of world languages, which are in constant competition with each other in the international arena. Globalization affects the conditions in which language learning takes place. In the modern world, the choice of language is often influenced by the economic component, that is, people begin to study a particular foreign language according to the priority of the country, for economic reasons. Moreover, globalization causes changes in the political conditions in which foreign languages are taught, for example, English. According to D. Crystal, "the natural condition of the changing state of languages leads us to the consciousness of a situation in which "no one has a monopoly on the English language" ..." [2, 6]. The issues of linguistic imperialism began to be investigated in the 90s of the twentieth century, which is primarily due to the global spread of the English language in all countries of the world. The term "linguistic imperialism" came into scientific use after the publication in 1992 of R. Philipson's book "Linguistic Imperialism" [3], the scientist understood by it the spread of English as a second language. According to Philipson, English should maintain its dominance in developing countries.

English occupies an important place in the communicative space in states where it has a certain status enshrined in legislative documents. For example, English is the official (state) language in the United Kingdom (the territory of the original distribution of the ethnic group), the United States, Canada, Australia and New Zealand, in which it is a means of

communication in all functional spheres. In countries such as India, South Africa, Pakistan, Malaysia, Philippines, Nigeria, Ghana, Bangladesh, Singapore, Germany, Switzerland, China, Austria and some others, English has the status of an official or second state language, along with the native national language. In the post-Soviet countries, English has the status of an auxiliary means of communication, adopted relatively recently and performing a limited set of communicative functions. Quite rightly, D. points out. The crystal points to the peculiarity of the English language "to be in the right place at the right time" [2, 145], which contributes to its formation as a "world leader and consolidation of positions in the spheres of interethnic communication" [2, 147].

Several factors contributed to the globalization of the English language. Firstly, it is the collapse of the colonial system in the late 60s of the last century, when English became the official or semi-official language of many liberated countries. Secondly, national economies have become more integrated into the global economy. Third, economic changes are closely related to technological innovations, since operations in global markets depend on the speed of information flows provided by the use of new communication technologies. New information and media technologies are increasingly invading the field of education, especially in the teaching of foreign languages, radically changing the practice of language learning.

The process of gradual and purposeful introduction of English into the field of education in almost all countries of the world has a great influence on the scale of the spread of the English language. Let's consider the process of spreading the English language in educational institutions of the Russian Federation and the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In Russia before the revolution, foreign languages were studied only by nobles and representatives of the diverse intelligentsia, that is, the elite of Russian society. The main foreign languages in educational institutions were Greek and Latin, which were considered classical and compulsory to study, since the vast majority of classical scientific works of that time were still written and published in these languages [4].

The main purpose of teaching foreign languages in the Russian Empire was to teach the student not the skills of free speech, but literary translation. In the XVIII-XIX centuries, everyday communication in foreign languages was accepted in wealthy noble families, the first of which was French. This cultural and educational phenomenon is most vividly represented in Leo Tolstoy's novel "War and Peace", a certain part of the novel was written by the writer in the form of letters in French.

In the Soviet Union, since the 1920s, approaches and forms of education, the goals of teaching languages, including foreign languages, have been changing. The main goal set for teachers during this period is to teach them to read, understand written and oral texts. Modern Western European languages are becoming relevant: English, German, French. Their study is connected with an urgent task for that time: "in a relatively minimal historical period to catch up and then surpass the level of industrial development of advanced countries" [4]. Since 1928, foreign languages have been a mandatory component of university programs in order to "make it mandatory for students to know at least one foreign language" [4]. This contributed to the gradual and high-quality teaching of foreign languages in Russian universities and helped to increase the role of this discipline.

Let's consider the situation with the study of foreign languages in Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan has developed a Concept for the development of foreign language education, which "from the standpoint of a new methodological approach defines the goals and content of foreign language education in accordance with international standards – the pan-European competencies of foreign language proficiency, which are a system of language proficiency levels and a system of describing these levels using a single system of concepts that can be used to describe any certification system, and, consequently, any training program, starting with the formulation of tasks – the goals of training and ending with the competencies achieved as a result of training" [5].

In addition, when teaching English, the state provides educational and methodological assistance, as well as experienced native-speaking teachers are involved, international experience and modern technologies are used. After all, the level of education is the starting point of economic and scientific and technological progress, the key to the successful development of Uzbekistan. Lagging behind in the field of education directly affects the country's competitiveness, national prospects and state security.

According to the "Trilingualism" program, the study of subjects of the mathematical cycle and natural sciences (chemistry, physics, biology) in English is gradually being introduced in Uzbekistan, however, despite huge efforts and financial investments in retraining personnel for teaching special disciplines in English, today many teachers of Uzbek schools do not yet possess the necessary level of knowledge of English language sufficient for teaching non-linguistic disciplines. This process should happen voluntarily, gradually.

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